

Adsorption Behaviour of Some Metal Ions on Cation-Exchange Resin (Dowex 50W-X4) from Ammonium Acetate-Dimethylformamide Media

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The cation-exchange (by Dowex 50W-X4; NH_4^+ -form) characteristics of 17 metal ions in media consisting of 40% DMF and varying concentrations (0.02-1.00M) of NH_4OAc have been reported. To ensure maximum adsorption, the metal concentrations employed were kept ca 16% of the total exchange capacity of the resin. The values of distribution coefficients have been evaluated, and possible separations of metal ions have been predicted. Some of the useful separations have been achieved using column chromatography.

ION-EXCHANGE characteristics of metal ions have largely been studied in ammonium acetate media and several metal ions have successfully been separated. The separations of Ba(II), Pb(II)¹, and of Mg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II) and Ba(II)² on R- NH_4 type resin in aqueous NH_4OAc have been investigated. Ward and Choppin³ determined the separation factors by column elution for Ce, Pm, Eu, Tb, Tm and Y using Dowex 50 and NH_4OAc solutions. A method for the ready separation of silver, lead and mercury(II) from each other has been developed by De and Majumdar⁴. In 1M acetate buffer, De and Sen⁵ were able to separate calcium and magnesium in dolomite and limestone. Dey and coworkers^{6,7} studied the adsorption behaviour of certain cations in HNO_3 - NH_4OAc and aqueous NH_4OAc , and reported an interesting procedure of separation of Ce(IV) from Ce(III), La(III) and other metal ions⁷.

The use of organic solvents in ion exchange separations of metals has become common place and hardly requires comment⁸. Since dimethylformamide is increasingly coming into use as a solvent, and mixed water-DMF solvents are now better understood, a detailed study of adsorption characteristics of the seventeen cations: Mg(II), Al(III), Ca(II), Cr(III), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Sr(II), Ag(I), Cd(II), Ba(II), La(III), Hg(II), Pb(II) and Th(IV), have been investigated in 40% v/v DMF-aq NH_4OAc media, using Dowex 50W-X4 (200-400 mesh, NH_4^+ -form) to exploit the possibility of better separations of the cations.

Experimental

Ion-Exchange Resin :

Dowex 50W-X4 (200-400 mesh) in H^+ -form was treated in a column successively with 1N HCl

and 1N NaOH before use. The resin was then converted into NH_4^+ -form by treating with 10% NH_4Cl solution in 10% liquor ammonia (Sp. gr. 0.91) and then washing with water till the effluent was free from chloride (negative test with AgNO_3). The resin was air-dried by suction on a sintered bed and stored, the capacity and the moisture content were 3.14 meq/g and ca 27.25%, respectively.

Metal Solutions :

Standard aqueous solutions (0.10-0.50M) of metal ions were prepared from their nitrates (B.D.H., AnalaR). Hg(II) nitrate was dissolved in aq NH_4OAc . The solutions were standardized as usual.

Ammonium Acetate Solution :

An aqueous solution of 6.0M NH_4OAc (E. Merck) was prepared and was standardized by the indirect determination of ammonia.

Buffer Solutions :

Buffer solutions of $p\text{H}=10$ (NH_4Cl /ammonia) and of $p\text{H}=5$ (NaOAc/HCl) were used for EDTA titrations. Other desired $p\text{H}$ were obtained by maintaining the $p\text{H}$ of the solution by the addition of suitable quantities of acid or alkali and with the help of a $p\text{H}$ -meter. $p\text{H}$ indicator papers (B.D.H.) were also used in some cases during titrations.

Organic Solvent :

Reagent-grade dimethylformamide (B.D.H.) was used.

pH Measurements and Equilibration of the System :

A Philips precision $p\text{H}$ -meter PR 9405M was employed for the $p\text{H}$ measurements. The solutions

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were mechanically shaken using a reciprocating shaker (Sambros & Co., SR. No. SE 037) in glass-stoppered pyrex flasks (100 ml) in batch experiments.

Distribution Studies

For the determination of distribution coefficients (D) by the batch equilibration method, 1.000 gram of the air-dried resin (NH_4^+ -form) was added to the mixture solutions containing the metal ion, DMF and NH_4OAc (total volume 25 ml), and shaken for 1 hr (it was previously ascertained that this time was adequate to attain equilibrium). The resin was filtered and the metal ion determined in an aliquot of the filtrate titrimetrically against EDTA, and the D values were obtained

$$D = \frac{\text{meq. metal ion per gram resin}}{\text{meq. metal ion per ml solution}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The metal concentrations employed were ca 16% of the total exchange capacity of the resin, to ensure maximum intake by the resin. Aqueous NH_4OAc used were 0.02, 0.06, 0.10, 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00M and DMF was 40%. Studies were made at a room temperature of $30 \pm 2^\circ$. The relative experimental errors in the determination of the D values were $\pm 10\%$ and $\pm 20\%$ for low and high D values, respectively.

Column Chromatography :

Before the chromatographic separations, the resin bed was prepared by making a slurry of the resin (5.0 g) in water and transferred to the graduated column. The length of the resin bed was ca 6 cm. The resin bed thus prepared was pretreated with 0.10M, 0.25M or 0.50M NH_4OAc as the case may be.

The feed (25 ml) was prepared by mixing standard solutions of the metal ions and aq. NH_4OAc (of appropriate concentration) and 40% DMF. It was then passed through the resin bed and the rate of flow was adjusted to 1.0 ± 0.3 ml per minute. The metal ions were determined in 5 ml effluent fractions.

Results and Discussion

The distribution coefficient (D) of the cations are reported in Table 1. In all the cases the sorption of metal ions decreases with increasing the concentrations of NH_4OAc (DMF being constant). Generally, the metal ion forms a complex with the acetate ion and the sorption depends upon the nature of complex formed. If the charge on the complex is positive, zero or negative, the sorption will be less⁷. The concentration 40% of DMF has been found to be best for separations, by trial experiments.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS (D) IN NH_4OAc -40% DMF($30 \pm 2^\circ$)

Cation	Distribution Coefficient					
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)
Mg(II)	355	195	110	40.3	14.8	1.1
Al(III)	>10 ⁴	>10 ⁴	>10 ⁴	2730	38.3	8
Ca(II)	581	293	184	36.2	15.4	4.1
Cr(III)	1810	272	97.2	19.6	11.3	7.1
Mn(II)	424	236	111	24.5	7	0.4
Co(II)	686	255	121	31	7.6	1.2
Ni(II)	851	224	125	30.7	7.6	1.5
Cu(II)	428	90.4	38.7	7.2	1.6	0.0
Zn(II)	422	142	60	9.7	0.2	0.0
Sr(II)	1070	578	284	93.2	31	9.5
Ag(I)	95.7	52.4	36.5	(*)	(*)	(*)
Cd(II)	429	107	46.7	7.0	0.3	0.0
Ba(II)	8070	784	433	190	57.8	20.7
La(III)	984	984	342	44.2	5.6	0.6
Hg(II)	(*)	(*)	(*)	140	45.8	9.7
Pb(II)	332	67	27.6	4.3	0.5	0.0
Th(IV)	>10 ⁴	>10 ⁴	6130	77.5	9.8	0.5

Overall concentrations of ammonium acetate (M) :
 (a)=0.02 ; (b)=0.06 ; (c)=0.10 ; (d)=0.25 ; (e)=0.50 ; (f)=1.00 ;
 (*)=precipitation.

As the concentration of NH_4OAc is increased, acetate ion replaces the coordinating water molecules resulting in the formation of complex species of a small positive charge, and consequently D is lowered. A further increase in the concentration of NH_4OAc leads to the formation of a neutral species and this also results in a decrease of D . When the concentration of NH_4OAc is higher, and a neutral metal acetate is likely to be present in solution, the predominant species in the resin phase would be $\text{M}^{\text{II}}(\text{OAc})^+$ or $\text{M}^{\text{III}}(\text{OAc})^{2+}$, as inferred by earlier workers^{8,9}.

It is of interest to refer to the work of Strelow and coworkers⁸, in which a detailed cation exchange study of a large number of metal ions has been reported from ethanol-HCl mixtures. The table of distribution coefficients clearly indicates that the role of ethanol is mainly to assist the formation of chlorocomplexes by influencing the dielectric constant of the media. In a likewise manner, in the work reported here, the role of DMF is also similar, and DMF does not display a complexing ability in the systems.

Ag(I) has slightly lower D values, whereas Al(III) and Th(IV) have slightly higher D values at lower concentration (0.02 M) of NH_4OAc , which is due to the higher affinity of ammonium ions towards the resin as compared to Ag^+ , and the reverse is true for Al(III) and Th(IV). Also, the sorption of Al(III) and Th(IV) is high in 0.1M NH_4OAc as compared to the other metal ions, which is due to the higher charge on these cations. The D values of Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) are zero in 1.0M NH_4OAc , whereas Ba(II) has a slightly higher D value ; hence Ba(II) can be separated from Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) in this concentration

range of NH_4OAc . The percentage loadings* of the metal ions under experiment are plotted against concentrations of ammonium acetate. In order to avoid overlapping of the plots for other cations, they have been divided into two groups,

- (1) Mg(II) , Ca(II) , Ni(II) , Sr(II) , Ag(I) , Cd(II) , Ba(II) , La(III) , Pb(II) and Th(IV) , and
- (2) Al(III) , Cr(III) , Mn(II) , Co(II) , Cu(II) , Zn(II) and Hg(II) ,

and shown separately in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively, which illustrate the separation possibilities.

Table 2 represents the variation of sorption of cations at the different concentrations of NH_4OAc

Fig. 1. Plot of Loading percentage vs concentration of ammonium acetate.

Mg(II) , Ca(II) , Ni(II) , Sr(II) , Ag(I) , Cd(II) , Ba(II) , La(III) , Pb(II) and Th(IV) .

Fig. 2. Plot of Loading percentage vs concentration of ammonium acetate, Al(III) , Cr(III) , Mn(II) , Co(II) , Cu(II) , Zn(II) and Hg(II) .

in 40% DMF. Few important chromatographic separations, i.e.

- (i) Th(IV) and Cu(II) ,
- (ii) Hg(II) and $\text{Pb(II)/Zn(II)/Cd(II)}$,
- (iii) Al(III) and $\text{Cu(II)/Zn(II)/Pb(II)/Cd(II)/Mn(II)/Cr(III)}$

were achieved at 0.10M, 0.25M and 0.50M NH_4OAc and few of them are shown in Figs. 3, 4 and 5, respectively. The elution characteristics¹⁰ are shown in Table 3, while Table 4 shows the quantitative values. Some of the binary separations are important, as may be seen from the Table.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF SORPTION OF CATIONS WITH THE CONCENTRATION OF AMMONIUM ACETATE (OVERALL DMF 40%)

$[\text{NH}_4\text{OAc}]$	Sorption order
1. 0.02	$\text{Al} \approx \text{Th} > \text{Ba} > \text{Cr} > \text{Sr} > \text{La} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Ca} > \text{Cd} > \text{Cu} \approx \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} > \text{Mg} > \text{Pb} > \text{Ag}$
2. 0.06	$\text{Al} \approx \text{Th} > \text{La} > \text{Ba} > \text{Sr} > \text{Ca} > \text{Cr} > \text{Co} > \text{Mn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Mg} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Cu} > \text{Pb} > \text{Ag}$
3. 0.10	$\text{Al} > \text{Th} > \text{Ba} > \text{La} > \text{Sr} > \text{Ca} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Mn} \approx \text{Mg} > \text{Cr} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd} > \text{Cu} \approx \text{Ag} > \text{Pb}$
4. 0.25	$\text{Al} > \text{Ba} > \text{Hg} > \text{Sr} > \text{Th} > \text{La} > \text{Mg} > \text{Ca} > \text{Co} \approx \text{Ni} > \text{Mn} > \text{Cr} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cu} > \text{Cd} > \text{Pb}$
5. 0.50	$\text{Ba} > \text{Hg} > \text{Al} > \text{Sr} > \text{Ca} > \text{Mg} > \text{Cr} > \text{Th} > \text{Co} \approx \text{Ni} \approx \text{Mn} \approx \text{La} > \text{Cr} > \text{Pb} > \text{Cd} \approx \text{Zn}$
6. 1.00	$\text{Ba} > \text{Hg} \approx \text{Sr} \approx \text{Al} \approx \text{Cr} > \text{Ca} > \text{Ni} \approx \text{Co} \approx \text{Mg} > \text{La} > \text{Th} \approx \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} \approx \text{Cu} \approx \text{Cd} \approx \text{Pb}$

* $L(\%) = \frac{\text{meq. of metal/g of resin}}{\text{meq. of metal initially taken}} \times 100.$

Fig. 3. Elution curves of Cu(II) and Th(IV) on Dowex 50W-X4 Resin (200-400 mesh, NH_4^+ -form) column.

Fig. 5. Elution curves of Al(III)-Cu(II)/Zn(II)/Cd(II) on Dowex 50W-X4 resin (200-400 mesh, NH_4^+ -form) column.

Fig. 4. Elution curves of Hg(II)-Zn(II)/Cd(II)/Pb(II) on Dowex 50W-X4 resin (200-400 mesh NH_4^+ -form) column.

TABLE 3—ELUTION CHARACTERISTICS¹⁰ OF METAL IONS

Metal Ions	BTV (ml)	VEP (ml)	TEV (ml)	Eluting agent in 40% DMF	NH_4OAc [M]
Cu(II)	100	200	300		0.10
Cu(II)	20	40	95		0.25
Zn(II)	10	45	105		0.25
Pb(II)	10	45	90		0.25
Cd(II)	5	55	110		0.25
Mn(II)	35	105	345		0.25
Cr(III)	15	70	230		0.25
Pb(II)	10	25	70		0.50
Zn(II)	10	35	80		0.50
Cd(II)	10	35	70		0.50

BTV=breakthrough volume, VEP=volume elution peak, TEV=terminal elution volume.

TABLE 4—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES. (FIRST ION MENTIONED IN THE MIXTURE IS ELUTED, WHILE THE SECOND ION IS THAT WHICH IS RETAINED)

Mixture	Eluting agent	Metal ion eluted		Eluting agent	Metal ion retained	
		Taken (mg)	Found (mg)		Taken (mg)	Found (mg)
Cu(II)-Th(IV)	(d)	32.89	33.23 ± 0.46	(a)	52.79	53.25 ± 0.29
Cu(II)-Al(III)	(e)	32.89	32.85 ± 0.12	(b)	8.39	8.49 ± 0.12
Zn(II)-Al(III)	(e)	32.46	33.04 ± 0.55	(b)	8.39	8.36 ± 0.10
Pb(II)-Al(III)	(e)	105.05	104.86 ± 0.16	(b)	8.39	8.39 ± 0.08
Cd(II)-Al(III)	(e)	54.07	54.92 ± 0.64	(b)	8.39	8.40 ± 0.14
Mn(II)-Al(III)	(e)	27.88	27.94 ± 0.10	(b)	8.39	8.38 ± 0.12
Cr(III)-Al(III)	(e)	16.12	15.82 ± 0.24	(b)	8.39	8.46 ± 0.12
Pb(II)-Hg(II)	(f)	101.32	101.23 ± 0.18	(c)	96.27	97.56 ± 0.86
Zn(II)-Hg(II)	(f)	32.43	32.72 ± 0.28	(c)	96.27	96.88 ± 0.24
Cd(II)-Hg(II)	(f)	54.07	54.47 ± 0.10	(c)	96.27	97.05 ± 0.55

(a) 3M HCl, (b) 5M HCl, (c) 2M aq NH_4OAc , (d) 0.1M NH_4OAc in 40% DMF, (e) 0.25M NH_4OAc in 40% DMF, (f) 0.5M NH_4OAc in 40% DMF.

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